

NISC Cross-RISCC Survey Report

Assessing the RISCC: Priorities for and barriers to climate-informed invasive species management in the United States.

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Abstract

In recent decades, substantial evidence has accumulated regarding the effects of climate change on the establishment, spread, and impact of invasive species — and, to a lesser degree, how invasive species erode resilience of native ecosystems to the impacts of climate change. This evidence highlights the need for a variety of targeted management strategies and approaches to protect ecosystems. While the importance of incorporating climate change into invasive species

management and policy is becoming more widely recognised, practitioner experiences and perspectives are rarely included in the development and delivery of invasion science, decision-support tools, decision-making, and policy. As a result, there may be misalignment between the science and practice of managing invasive species under a changing climate. To better understand practitioner's challenges and priorities, the Regional Invasive Species and Climate Change (RISCC) Management Networks surveyed invasive species practitioners and researchers across the United States (U.S.). Results of these surveys offer a wealth of information that could benefit national prioritization efforts, yet to date these data have only been reported at regional levels. Here, we compare the survey responses from five RISCC regions to identify common priorities and challenges associated with the management of invasive species in a changing climate. Collectively, survey respondents reported that, despite its perceived importance, only 24% of management and research time is dedicated towards emerging invasive species challenges. Common barriers to climate-informed invasive species management include limited time, funding, and personnel. Identifying ecosystems resilient to invasive species was consistently noted as a high priority for managers, followed by identifying range-shifting taxa and understanding the impacts of climate change on the effectiveness of control strategies (i.e. mechanical, chemical, and biological control). Together these results demonstrate the critical need for incorporating climate change into invasive species management in all regions of the U.S. and highlight research and policy topics that align with management needs to address the interacting stressors of invasive species and climate change.

Introduction

Invasive species – non-native taxa whose introduction causes or is likely to cause socio-economic or environmental harm or harm to human, animal, or plant health (Executive Order No. 13751, 2016) – and climate change are two of the leading anthropogenic threats to species and ecosystems, including human communities. Together these stressors can cause widespread negative impacts on native biodiversity, ecosystem function, human health and wellbeing, and agricultural production (IPBES, 2019; IPCC, 2022; Lodge et al., 2006; Pejchar & Mooney, 2009). Addressing the dual threats of climate change and invasive species requires effective, evidence-based management strategies as well as regional and national coordination in policy and regulations (Hellmann et al., 2008; Pyke et al., 2008). Invasive species management is more time and cost effective if implemented proactively before a species is established and spreading (Cuthbert et al., 2022; Pyke et al., 2008). Similarly, coordinated management responses across regions or jurisdictions can facilitate proactive management of invasive species before they spread and establish in new areas (Lodge et al., 2006, 2016). Despite widespread knowledge of these best practices, management decisions are typically made in isolation at smaller, local-to-regional scales, making it difficult to identify shared challenges, priorities, and resources at broader spatial scales (Beaury et al., 2020; Simberloff et al., 2005). Additionally, decisions related to regulation and policy often occur at a national scale, frequently overlooking the

experiences and perspectives of practitioners who are implementing and evaluating management actions (DeWitt et al., 2006; Epanchin-Niell et al., 2010). Consequently, more communication and collaboration is needed between invasive species practitioners, researchers, and policy and decision-makers across multiple spatial scales.

Across the invasive species management and academic communities, there is an appreciation for the need to engage with people who work in different sectors through boundary-spanning efforts (Esler et al., 2010; Morelli et al., 2021; Shackleton et al., 2019, 2022). Yet, many core values and perspectives in invasion ecology – including those related to management and climate concern – differ between groups (Shackleton et al., 2022). Socioeconomic, cultural, and institutional context influences the values and perspectives of individuals, with academics, for example, typically focusing on basic research topics that garner higher citations, which do not always address the core information needs of practitioners (Esler et al., 2010; Hallett et al., 2017; Matzek et al., 2015; Wehi et al., 2023). Such context-based discrepancies could affect the level of perceived risk for different invasive species leading to different management strategies in different areas. Additionally, failure to consider climate change as part of invasive species management could also influence not just the effectiveness of management strategies, but also the abilities of regulatory agencies to fulfill their statutory duties (Dukes et al., 1999; Pyke et al., 2008). With invasive species traversing geopolitical boundaries (Keller et al., 2011; Perrings et al., 2010), coupled with the rising costs associated with invasive species management (Cuthbert et al., 2022) and impacts (Turbelin et al., 2023), there is an urgent need to identify if and how priorities for invasive species management in a changing climate align or diverge across broad management scales.

As a response to practitioner requests for actionable science on how to adapt invasive species management in a changing climate, Regional Invasive Species and Climate Change (RISCC) Management Networks have been established to build stronger researcher-practitioner partnerships across the United States (U.S.), including in the Northeast (NE), Southeast (SE), North Central (NC), Northwest (NW), and Pacific Islands (PI) (Figure 1) These regional networks function as boundary-spanning organizations working at the interface of research and practice. The RISCCs utilize the Translational Invasion Ecology (TIE) framework (Morelli et al. 2021) to co-produce actionable science with practitioners at the intersection of climate change and invasive species and facilitate dialog between the research and management communities. As a first step to better understanding regional challenges and priorities, the RISCC Management Networks surveyed managers and researchers in their respective regions. To date, this information has only been summarized at the regional level and in individual RISCC reports as these surveys were originally intended to inform the resources and activities developed by the RISCC groups. Yet, when integrated it represents a wealth of information that could benefit national prioritization, such as informing the work of the National Invasive Species Council (NISC), which facilitates the coordination of invasive species work across U.S. federal agencies.

Here, we synthesize the collective results of five regional RISCC surveys to better understand the overall research and policy needs relating to the compounding threats of invasive species and climate change on ecosystems and communities in the U.S. Through this synthesis, we identify and compare barriers to invasive species management and to the incorporation of climate change into invasive species management decisions, as well as discover the core sources of information for informing management decisions. Given the role of the RISCC networks as boundary-spanning organizations, we also evaluate if and how invasion opinions related to invasive species and climate change differ between researchers and practitioners when identifying areas to focus TIE efforts. Lastly, we offer examples of strategies the regional RISCC teams have employed to address a diversity of barriers to managing invasive species under climate change.

Materials and Methods

Surveys and Survey Populations

Leadership teams at each of the five RISCC networks developed and conducted regional surveys ranging in length from 15 to 25 questions that were in multiple choice, select-all-that-apply, 3-point to 5-point Likert scales, ranking, sliding scale, and short answer formats ([Appendix 1](#)). The questions were related to invasive species management and research priorities, challenges associated with incorporating climate change into invasive species management, management information including scale of management work, location(s) of work, and employer, level of concern about climate change impacts on invasive species management, and resources used to inform management decisions. Each RISCC network was established at a different time (see [Appendix 2](#) and [3](#)) and is structured slightly differently. For example, the NE RISCC is the longest running group; it runs on a model of long weekly meetings of a large, distributed leadership primarily composed of researchers including students and postdoctoral researchers at academic institutes. In contrast, the NW RISCC, NC RISCC, and PI RISCC groups are run by a few researchers and staff members but with advisory boards made up of state and federal resource managers that meet monthly or bimonthly. Finally, the SE RISCC has a more complex structure, including an advisory board but with coordinators for different activities and sectors as well. Though collaborative, the five RISCC networks function independently, thus resulting in varying survey structure and questions. The SE and NC RISCCs included separate sets of questions for participants who were practitioners vs. university-based researchers/extension professionals, while all other RISCCs had one set of questions for all participants ([Appendix 1](#)). Invitations to participate in each survey were sent out via email to a total of 17 unique listservs, three manually curated lists of invasive species stakeholders/rightsholders, and one social media group; see [Appendix 2](#). Responses from each region were gathered over a period of several weeks (for survey dates see [Appendix 3](#)).

We evaluated survey responses across three groupings of respondents, detailed below: nationwide, regional, and based on respondents' occupational role (managers versus researchers) at each of the regional scales. We defined the nationwide scale as any respondent from the five RISCC surveys who indicated they worked within at least one U.S. state or territory.

For regional results, we only included respondents from each RISCC survey who indicated they worked within one of the states or territories included in their respective RISCC network (Figure 1, [Appendix 3](#)). For the Northeast RISCC (NE RISCC) these included Connecticut, Delaware, Illinois, Indiana, Iowa, Kentucky, Maine, Maryland, Massachusetts, Michigan, Minnesota, Missouri, New Hampshire, New Jersey, New York, Ohio, Pennsylvania, Rhode Island, Virginia, Vermont, West Virginia, and Wisconsin. For Southeast RISCC (SE RISCC) these included Florida, Georgia, South Carolina, North Carolina, Mississippi, Tennessee, Arkansas, Puerto Rico, and the U.S. Virgin Islands. For North Central RISCC (NC RISCC) these included Montana, Colorado, Kansas, Nebraska, North Dakota, South Dakota and Wyoming. For Northwest RISCC (NW RISCC) these included Washington, Oregon, and Idaho. The Pacific Islands RISCC (PI RISCC) survey included only participants working in Hawai'i, as the US-Affiliated Pacific Islands were added to the PI RISCC group after the survey was conducted.

Finally, to evaluate responses based on occupation, we subsetted the regional dataset into two groups based on answers to occupation and/or employer questions (see [Appendix 1](#)). Researchers were classified as respondents who self-identified as researchers, worked as "scientists," worked in "research", or indicated they worked at a university/academic institution. Managers were classified as participants who did not work at university/academic institutions and/or self-identified as managers or practitioners in a survey question ([Appendix 1](#)). For all analyses, we excluded responses from participants who indicated they did not work with invasive species in any capacity. Identifying information was removed from all survey data. We aggregated responses to each question to ensure anonymity of respondents.

Figure 1 United States (U.S.) states and territories that were included in each of the five Regional Invasive Species and Climate Change (RISCC) Management Networks at the time when survey responses were collected for each region. Note that the Pacific Islands RISCC now includes the US-Affiliated Pacific Islands, the Northwest RISCC also covers adjacent Canadian territories and the western portion of Montana, and the Northeast RISCC no-longer includes the Midwest states of Minnesota, Iowa, Missouri, Wisconsin, Illinois, Indiana, Michigan, and Ohio.

Data Analysis

Sample sizes for each question for each group (nationwide, regional, and occupation) varied as respondents were not required to answer all survey questions and no minimum completion rate was required for any of the surveys. Similarly, for some questions (such as the spatial scale at which they worked, respondents could select multiple response options. Therefore, results are reported relative to the sample size for each question and sample sizes for some questions may exceed the number of unique participants. Unanswered questions (where answers were left completely blank) were excluded from analyses but partial survey answers (e.g., if some but not all response options were selected or ranked) were included to account for respondents who only selected response options that applied to them. In some cases, the wording, response options, or format of questions differed across surveys. When this occurred, we categorized responses into

groups based on their similarity for analysis (see [Appendix 1](#)). As a result, the number of votes (responses) for some questions (e.g., invasive species priority categories) may exceed the number of unique participants. For details on response groupings see [Appendix 1](#). For Likert scale questions, we assigned a value of 1 to N number of response options. Some Likert scale questions varied in the number of response options (e.g., 3-point scale compared to 5-point scale). In these cases, we converted 5-point scales to 3-point scales by collapsing Likert response categories 1 and 2 and collapsing Likert response categories 4 and 5 ([Appendix 1](#)) (Jacoby & Matell, 1971). Similarly, when question formatting differed between the surveys (e.g., “select all that apply” versus Likert scale) we converted Likert scale questions into binary responses by collapsing responses that indicated some form of agreement/usefulness (“Occasionally”, “Frequently”, “Sometimes”, “Often”, “Always”, “Extremely”) a value of 1 while forms of disagreement (e.g., “Not/Rarely”, “Not at all”, “Never”) were assigned a value of 0. We analyzed Likert scale questions using nonparametric Kruskal-Wallis Rank Sum Tests and evaluated pairwise comparisons using Wilcoxon tests followed by a Bonferroni correction to adjust for multiple comparisons. To assess how employer, scale of management, or occupation affected level of concern about climate change, priorities, and barriers in invasive species management, we compared responses using a Wilcoxon test for pairwise comparisons and used the Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons. Lastly, we tested for differences in the proportion of time spent managing current and new (future) invasions with a two-sample z-test. All analyses were performed in R version 4.1.2 (R Core Team, 2023).

Results

Respondent Demographics

The cross-RISCC surveys included responses from a total of 845 individuals who were involved in invasive species work within the U.S. states and territories. At the regional scale, 130 respondents worked in the NE RISCC region, 120 in the SE RISCC, 58 in the NC RISCC, 273 in the NW RISCC, and 59 in the PI RISCC. Of these 640 regional responses (76% of nationwide total), 534 individuals were invasive species managers (83%) and 106 (17%) were invasive species researchers and/or worked primarily at an academic institution. The other 205 respondents (24% of the nationwide total) worked outside of the states and territories covered within their RISCC region and were included in the 845 responses that were analyzed at the nationwide scale. The states within which respondents most frequently worked were Washington (n=164) and Oregon (n=125), followed by New York (n=93), and Florida (n=74); responses were received from individuals working in all states except North Dakota, Oklahoma, and Wyoming.

At the organizational scale, 658 respondents nationwide categorized their employer and nearly half indicated they worked for a government agency; most were based in federal (26%) or state (15%) agencies, followed by county (10%) or municipal (8%) positions. Fourteen percent of

respondents worked for non-profit organizations, 13% were in academia, and the remaining represented private individuals (6%), tribal nations (4%), or had other affiliations (4%), including Partnership for Regional Invasive Species Management (PRISM) groups, contractors, and watershed districts/partnerships. The percentages of respondents from each of these employers varied across regions (Table S1; [Appendix 4](#), Fig S1; [Appendix 5](#)): NC RISCC respondents were mostly employed by county governments (32%, n=20/63) and academic institutions (27%, n=17/63); NE RISCC respondents primarily worked for the state (26%, n=34/130) or non-governmental organizations (25%, n=33/130); most SE RISCC respondents worked for the state (26%, n=30/116) and academia (23%, n= 27/116); NW RISCC respondents predominantly worked for the federal government (39%, n=83/214) followed by county governments (18%, n=39/214); and almost half of PI RISCC respondents worked for the federal government (45%, n=27/60) followed by state government (18%, n=11/60) .

Spatially, the majority (33%) of invasive species work nationwide (n= 347/1033 responses) was conducted at the watershed scale (the smallest spatial scale option) followed by the state (27%) scale. Across those surveyed, only 1% conducted invasive species work at a national (country) scale, with the remaining equally split across regional (multiple states) (19%) and landscape (multiple watersheds) (19%) scales (Table S2; [Appendix 4](#)).

Management and knowledge

When asked how much of their management time is spent working on currently established invasive taxa versus new (likely to, but not yet established) taxa, respondents nationwide (n=585) indicated that they spent significantly more time working with currently established invasive taxa (76%) than with new invasives (24%) ($z = 38.825, p < 0.001$). This trend was also observed within each of the five RISCC regions and for both researchers and managers (Table S3; [Appendix 4](#)).

When asked about the success of current invasive species management, 40% (n= 245/610) of respondents nationwide said they were holding their ground with invasive species while 39%, (n=236/610) said they were losing ground. Just 21% (n=129/610) of respondents felt that they were gaining ground against invasives. These management sentiments differed slightly across the four RISCC regions that asked this question, with the majority of NE and SE respondents indicating they were losing ground against invasives (59%, n=77/130 and 49%, n=43/92 respectively), whereas the NC and NW regions were predominantly static (neither gaining nor losing) (51%, n=19/37 and 47% n=132/271 respectively, Table S4, [Appendix 4](#)).

With respect to the level of concern about climate change impacts on invasive species management, nationwide we found that the sentiments of individual respondents differed from perceived sentiments of their employer (Fig 2, Kruskal-Wallis $X^2 = 272.51, df=1, p < 0.01$). While most individuals (62%, n=410/664) said they were “very concerned” about climate change

impacts, just 35% (n=193/556) perceived their organizations to be very concerned. This trend was consistent within the four RISCC regions that compared levels of concern between individuals (“very concerned” range: 42% – 75%) and the perceived level of concern of their organizations (“very concerned” range: 21% – 47%) (Fig 2, Table S5, [Appendix 4](#)).

The extent to which respondents perceived their organizations to be concerned about climate change effects on invasive species management varied across the four RISCC regions that asked this question (Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 23.275, df = 3, $p < 0.001$), with respondents in the NE and NW indicated greater levels of concern within their respective organizations compared to those in the SE and NC regions (Table S6, [Appendix 4](#)). Similarly, individual levels of concern varied significantly across all five regions (Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 24.168, df = 4, $p < 0.001$), with individuals from the NE more frequently very concerned about climate change compared to individuals from the SE, NC and NW regions and marginally more concerned than respondents from the PI region (Table S6, [Appendix 4](#)). Respondents from the NW were also more frequently very concerned about climate change than those from NC (Bonferroni $p = 0.024$). Across all five regions, individuals from the NC showed the least overall concern about the impacts of climate change on invasive species management.

Fig. 2. Levels of individual concern about climate change impacts on invasive species management across the United States (nationwide) and the five RISCC regions compared to their perceived levels of concern at the organizations where they work. PI RISCC did not include a question about perceived organization concern in their survey (see [Appendix 1](#)).

Invasive Species Management Priorities

When comparing how respondents nationwide ranked the priority level of six management and research topics, identifying resilient communities was most frequently ranked as “high” priority (55%, n=466/850 votes), followed by identifying range shifting taxa (46%, n=388/845 votes). There was a three-way tie for the third-highest priority topic, between control methods (42%, n=364/867 votes), pathways of invasion (42%, n=353/841 votes), and invasive species impacts (42%, n=688/1641 votes) (Fig 3, Tables S7 and S8, [Appendix 4](#)). Sleeper species were most frequently identified as a “low” priority both nationwide (36%, n=234/657 votes) and at regional scales across the five RISCC networks (Fig 3, Tables S7 and S8, [Appendix 4](#)). Similar topics were identified as “high” priorities across the four spatial scales of management (region, state, landscape, and watershed) and across employment organization (Fig S2, Appendix5); with resilience and range-shifting taxa consistently identified among the top priorities (Fig 4). Respondents who work at a state scale ranked five of the six management topics as “high” priority, with only sleeper species being ranked much lower (Fig 4, Table S8; Appendix 4). Sleeper species were also consistently ranked as the lowest “high” priority topic across respondents, regardless of employment organization, although concern about other topics (e.g. invasive species impacts) varied slightly across employment organizations (Fig S2, Appendix 5).

Fig 3 Percent of responses by survey participants across the United States (nationwide) and within each RISCC region when asked to rank each invasive species research topic in terms of “low”, “medium” or “high” priority for informing management. Percentages are reported relative to the sample size for each individual research topic that was offered as a response option in each RISCC surveys (see Table S7, [Appendix 4](#))

While some research topics were consistently identified as high priorities across all five RISCC regions, there was also considerable variation in priority rankings regionally (Fig 4). For example, despite resilience being identified as the highest priority nationwide, resilience received the lowest proportion of high-priority responses in the NW and SE RISCC surveys (Fig 4, Table S8, [Appendix 4](#)). Similarly, identifying range-shifting taxa (the fourth most important priority nationwide) was the highest priority topic for three of the five RISCC regions (NW, SE, and PI), yet was a much lower priority (third to last among high-priority topics) for the NE (Fig 3). Two RISCC regions had a topic ranked within their top three high-priority topics that was omitted from the nationwide analysis as it was not included as a response option in all five RISCC surveys. These highly ranked topics were phenological shifts (NE RISCC), and impacts of extreme environmental events (PI RISCC) (Fig 4, Table S8, [Appendix 4](#)).

The distribution of survey respondent opinions on invasive species management topics varied across the regional RISCC groups. Responses in the NE and NC surveys were skewed towards

the "high" priority response option, while the opposite trend was observed in the SE where more respondents selected "low" priority when ranking invasive species topics. Respondents from the PI showed a bimodal distribution with similar percentages selecting the "low" and "high" options when ranking priority topics while in the NW, RISCC respondents showed nearly equal selection of "low", "medium", and "high" priorities (Fig S3; [Appendix 5](#)).

Fig 4: Invasive species management priorities identified by RISCC survey respondents nationwide and across varying spatial scales from largest to smallest: national, region, state, landscape, and watershed. Percentages are reported relative to the sample size for each research topic within each spatial scale.

Barriers to Invasive Species and Climate Change Management

There were similar barriers to invasive species management (on its own) and incorporating climate change into invasive species management both nationwide and at regional RISCC scales. The greatest barriers for both invasive species management and incorporating climate change into invasive species management were funding and personnel (Fig 3). These barriers were also consistently identified as limiting both invasive species management and incorporating climate

change into management across employers (for details on employer-based variation see Fig S4 and S5; [Appendix 5](#)). Differences in institute (employer) priorities and the socio-political landscape were also important constraints and were significantly more limiting for invasive species management than for incorporating climate change into management activities (Kruskal Wallis $X^2 = 6.088$, $df=1$, $p = 0.0136$ and Kruskal Wallis $X^2 = 18.864$, $df=1$, $p < 0.001$ respectively). One of the biggest differences in the barriers between invasive species management and incorporating climate change into management decisions related to lack of access or availability of information (Fig 3). Although information was somewhat limiting for invasive species management, it was a significantly greater barrier to incorporating climate change into management (Fig 3; Kruskal Wallis $X^2 = 53.702$, $df=1$, $p < 0.001$). Similarly, lack of expertise was a significantly greater barrier to managing under climate change than managing invasive species alone (Fig 3; Kruskal Wallis $X^2 = 36.592$, $df=1$, $p < 0.001$).

Fig 3 The percent of responses from respondents nationwide that identified potential barriers as Always/Often limiting, Sometimes limiting, or Rarely/Never limiting their success in managing invasive species (gray bars) or incorporating climate change into invasive species management (dark red bars).

Respondents most frequently selected knowledge from peers or stakeholders as a main source of information to inform management decisions (19%, n=865/4516 votes), followed by scientific literature (13%, n=587/4516 votes) and gray literature (11%, n=516/4516 votes). Just 2% (n=108/4516) of votes cast by respondents identified listservs as useful sources of information (Table S9; Appendix 4). For three of the five RISCC regions (NW, NC, and PI) peer and stakeholder knowledge was most frequently identified as a useful source of information by

respondents, while online resources were the most useful in the SE and workshops/symposia most frequently useful in the NE (Fig 4, [Table S9; Appendix 4](#)).

Fig 4 Sources of information that inform invasive species management nationwide and across the five RISCC regions.

Some sources of information used to inform invasive species work differed significantly between researchers and managers (Fig 5) with researchers relying significantly more frequently on online resources, and listservs compared to managers ([Table S9 and S10; Appendix 4](#)). In contrast, conversations with peers, stakeholder knowledge, and best practices documents were significantly more useful for managers than researchers (Fig 5, [Table S9 and S10; Appendix 4](#)). These differences were reflected in the relative utility of information sources across employer groupings, with peer/stakeholder knowledge more useful for respondents who work for governmental employees (federal or state) compared to those in academia (Fig S6, Appendix 5). The response options for sources of information varied across RISCC surveys and the utility of information sources included as response options in all five surveys also varied (Fig 5). At the regional level, few differences in information sources used by managers and researchers were statistically significant ([Table S10; Appendix 4](#)), except in the North Central region where land/spatial data were significantly more useful for researchers compared to managers while best

practices documents were significantly more useful for managers than researchers ([Table S10; Appendix 4](#)).

Fig 5 Information sources used by researchers and managers (practitioners) nationwide and for each of the five RISCC regions. See [Table S9 and S10; Appendix 4](#) for sample size details.

Discussion

The Importance of Climate-Smart Prevention and Ongoing Management

It is well established within the invasive species research and management communities that early (proactive) invasive species prevention and management (e.g., EDRR) are more efficient and less costly (or resource intensive) than reactive approaches and are likely the most effective way to protect ecosystems and communities. A proactive stance becomes even more critical when considering the compounding effects of climate change on current and future invasions. The majority of managers surveyed in this study, however, focus their efforts on currently established invasive taxa rather than surveying for new, yet-to-establish species that are likely to pose a threat in the future. This focus was reflected further in the high priority topics identified

by survey respondents, including many topics related to the management of individual invasive species or target communities. These reactive management strategies can be tied to ongoing challenges related to limited resources—particularly funding and personnel— or policy barriers that limit capacity to survey for, or control and manage species early in the invasion process (Beaury, Fusco, et al., 2021). For example, over 50% of resources by reporting federal agencies are dedicated to managing already established invasive species, despite federal directives to support cost-effective invasive species management (Executive Order No. 13751, 2016; Reaser et al., 2020). These barriers are amplified by a lack of knowledge and information on the effects of climate change on both invasive taxa and broader ecological assemblages. The persistence of these barriers both regionally and nationwide across the U.S. suggests these are core places where boundary-spanning organizations, like the RISCCs, can concentrate current and future TIE efforts.

Nationwide, identifying resilient ecosystems, range-shifting taxa, and impacts on control methods were the highest priority topics related to the management of invasive species under climate change. These topics are prime candidates for national prioritization for both new and expanded research programs and new and revised policies. These topics have been identified in other research prioritization studies (Beaury et al., 2020; Esler et al., 2010; Matzek et al., 2015; Ricciardi et al., 2021), and they share a common foundation of focusing on managing individual taxa or communities. Identifying and protecting resilient ecosystems is a management strategy that covers a spectrum of definitions and management goals (Lopez et al., 2021). Here we use the term to describe management that focuses on preserving core structural or functional components of ecosystems while allowing for some changes in species assemblage, which is an integral component of climate-smart conservation (Stein et al., 2014).

Identifying and managing resilient ecosystems is often dependent on identifying range-shifting taxa, which threaten to alter community composition and ecosystem functioning as they move into new areas (Wallingford et al., 2020). Consequently, invasive species can directly impede efforts to promote climate resiliency across a broad spectrum of socio-economic and environmental contexts (Roy et al., 2023). However, it will be impossible to eradicate or manage all invasive (or range-shifting) taxa, and because of a range of impacts and societal priorities, not all species will demand equivalent research or management investment. Thus, a more strategic process of prioritizing resource allocation to maximize conservation returns relative to goals is often a tangible strategy (Lynch et al., 2022). With ongoing funding and personnel constraints, these two priority topics focus broadly on the need to identify which locations and species to focus on for management. An ongoing need to support where and which invasive species to manage was further reflected in survey write-in responses, many of which mentioned lack of capacity for explicitly incorporating climate change into management decisions. Broad-scale changes to national priorities and paradigms, including integrating invasive species into climate change management will likely be necessary to meet climate adaptation goals.

Once an invasive species is established, chemical and mechanical control are the most common management strategies employed at smaller local or regional scales (Culliney, 2005; Sigg, 1998). Understanding how climate change may affect current control strategies was identified as a high priority by survey respondents nationwide. Climate-induced shifts in growing season can affect the timing of chemical or mechanical treatments, with longer seasons leading to the need for increased frequency and shifts in the onset of management interventions (Marushia et al., 2010; Monahan et al., 2016). Similarly, changes in species traits driven by climate, such as biomass, leaf or root structure, and behavior can make species more resistant to current dosage concentrations and application practices or reduce the effectiveness of biological control (Gould et al., 2020). This will likely result in the need to alter management tactics or employ more aggressive management prescriptions, for example by using higher concentrations or frequencies of chemical treatments or new biocontrol strategies (Ziska, 2020). Changes that will likely require updates to current policies and regulations include those that govern the registration and direction of use for pesticides (40 CFR 156.10(i)) and expediting biocontrol approval processes by addressing funding and bureaucracy barriers (DiTomaso et al., 2017).

For many taxa, however, the climate-change impacts on control techniques remain unknown (Ziska, 2020). Even for taxa with information on climate-induced impacts on control, changing the timing and intensity of current management strategies in response to climate change will likely require additional funding and personnel, two barriers that already limit invasive species management. As well, climate change may also necessitate increased flexibility on the part of funding agencies, when increased climate-related disturbances impact the ability of grantees to fulfill grant goals or objectives with short timelines. In some cases, overcoming these barriers may require institutional-level changes in employment structure (e.g., duration or timing of seasonal contracts), particularly for organizations that rely on temporary contract workers to implement control measures. Such changes could also include altering work hours (e.g., if environmental conditions, such as extreme heat, limit time that crews can work in the field), adding flexibility to timelines for project deliverables for grant-funded activities, or extending seasonal contracts to account for prolonged treatment schedules (a response that some respondents indicated is already being implemented by their organizations).

Regional Differences in Priority Topics

We also identified differences in high-priority topics that may benefit more from TIE efforts at regional scales. For example, respondents who work in the Pacific Islands more frequently identified extreme environmental events as a higher priority topic compared to other RISCC regions. Extreme events, such as tropical storms, severe wildfires, and hurricanes, can both transport invasive species via movement of materials and aid movement during or after an event, and can help species establish in new areas through ecosystem disturbance (Diez et al., 2012; Horvitz et al., 1998). The effects of extreme events can also alter the effectiveness of current management strategies. For example, wildlife sanctuaries and forest reserves on Hawai'i are

often protected by mammal-proof fencing, which limits the spread of non-native ungulates such as pigs, goats, and deer (Pejchar et al., 2020). Falling trees damage fences during storm events, which can take months to repair, and create opportunities for ungulates to access high quality habitat in protected wildlife sanctuaries, threatening native species. Invasive ungulates cause physical damage to native forest structure and biodiversity through feeding and rooting behavior and by promoting non-native species through disturbances (Nuñez et al., 2010). Additionally, ungulates can spread disease-causing insects like avian malaria-carrying mosquitos, which have devastated native Hawaiian birds (LaPointe, 2006), or forest pathogens including *Ceratocystis huliohia* and *C. lukuohia*, that lead to Rapid 'Ōhi'a Death (Perroy et al., 2021). This disease has affected over forty thousand hectares of 'Ōhi'a (*Metrosideros polymorpha*), leading to massive losses in native forest habitat in mesic areas of Hawai'i (Camp et al., 2019).

Regional differences in high-priority topics were not the only evidence we found to suggest that a one-size-fits-all approach may not be appropriate for allocating invasive species management resources across the U.S. Our results suggest a striking difference in the spread of priority votes across the RISCC regions, particularly in the southeast where votes were skewed towards low-priority votes. This low-priority skew could be driven by the high diversity of invasive species already established in the southeastern U.S. (Fujisaki et al., 2015; Hiatt et al., 2019), resulting in invasive species fatigue, or a focus on more tractable issues. Alternatively, this skew towards low priority votes may suggest respondents in the Southeast are more concerned about other priority topics not offered as options in the SE survey. Write-in responses commonly included climate impacts on control techniques, developing new methods of detection (e.g., using eDNA), and identifying invasive species that do not warrant ongoing or future management as topics of high priority.

Overcoming barriers through Regional Boundary-Spanning Organizations

Our work identified several differences between regions in the perceived barriers to managing invasive species under climate change. Differences in the priorities of respondents compared to their employers and the socio-political landscape within which respondents work were significantly greater barriers to invasive species management than for integrating climate change into invasive species management, reflecting a growing need for additional dedicated invasive species personnel at both regional and national scales. Survey respondents indicated that many climate-related policies and management decisions enacted and implemented by their organizations were centered around minimizing damage from natural disasters, including damage to infrastructure, or informing decisions related to planting native species rather than mitigating the spread and impacts of invasive species. While respondents frequently identified that invasive species can magnify these topics of concern for their organizations (i.e., natural disasters and restoration), management of invasive species to mitigate such impacts remains absent from many state and federal climate adaptation plans. Given that damages caused by invasive species are more costly than many natural disasters such as floods, drought, and

wildfire, and invasive species damage costs are rising at a faster rate than natural disasters (Turbelin et al., 2023), new or modified policies that treat biological invasions as natural disasters could be one strategy for increasing the resources and support of organizations for managing the spread and impact of invasive taxa while also managing for environmental changes.

One barrier for combining both invasive species and climate change management into existing management plans remains access to or availability of useful and relevant information; an area where boundary-spanning efforts can play a key role. The regional RISCC teams have employed a variety of strategies to address informational management barriers, including writing open-access summaries of scientific literature, developing syntheses on topics that interest managers, and creating online spaces where researchers and practitioners can interact and share knowledge reciprocally. This survey shows that information in the scientific and gray literature are useful, as are online resources and workshops symposia, which were all identified as important sources of information by one or multiple RISCC groups. Knowledge gained from peers, however, was the top way identified nationally that managers get information to do their work. Therefore, opportunities for knowledge exchange that emphasize peer-to-peer learning, such as workshops, conferences, networking or other social events that bring together managers with peers who are knowledgeable about climate-smart invasive species management, may be the most fruitful for overcoming informational barriers. The benefits of facilitating such boundary-spanning information exchanges are already apparent in the NE RISCC, the longest running regional RISCC network, where survey respondents indicated that workshops/symposia are most frequently useful for informing management decisions.

Another strategy successfully employed by the RISCCs to overcome information barriers has been to highlight existing resources on the nexus of invasive species management and climate change (NE RISCC, 2020). For example, the NC RISCC hosted a webinar series that shared information on online decision-making tools (e.g., INHABIT (Engelstad et al., 2022) and EDDMapS (Wallace and Barger 2014)) that are available for identifying potential range-shifting taxa. Similarly, the SE RISCC has hosted webinars on range-shifting invasive species, such as the Burmese python (*Python bivittatus*) and Joro spider (*Trichonephila clavata*), focused on promoting public awareness and informing future management strategies. Another successful strategy has been to synthesize information on new emerging threats when resources are absent or inaccessible. NW RISCC, for example, developed a management brief (fact sheet) that overviewed the life cycle, invasion history, and climate-smart management options for the invasive emerald ash borer (*Agrilus planipennis*), which recently established populations in the region. A third successful approach has been to gather together researchers, managers, and community members for facilitated discussions to share lessons learned and best practices. For example, the NE RISCC has created a series of online events including interactive discussions called “coffee talks” on topics including resilience and range-shifting taxa, as well as a virtual

speed networking event that provided a virtual space for researchers and practitioners to connect and discuss invasive species management topics and techniques.

Another potential barrier to the development of climate-smart invasive species management approaches is the lack of transdisciplinary research on particular topics. Transdisciplinary research is becoming increasingly important in the field of invasion ecology as teams seek to incorporate a wider variety of stakes- and rights-holders when conducting risk assessment and impacts (Morelli et al., 2021). RISCC groups have worked to fill this gap through original research projects conducted by diverse teams or by facilitating science co-production with partners to fill information gaps. Seventy percent of the PI RISCC respondents desired to see more collaborative research projects related to climate change and invasive species management in the region. In response, the PI RISCC group facilitated the initiation of a project involving the U.S. Geological Survey and natural-resource managers on Hawai'i Island that focuses on exploring various invasive-species and climate change management scenarios leveraging the Resist, Accept, Direct (RAD) framework (Lynch et al., 2022). Similarly, the NE RISCC has undertaken a variety of original research projects focused on identifying high-risk range-shifting taxa (e.g., see Allen and Bradley, 2016), making results available as peer-reviewed journal articles, research summaries, and online tools such as one created in collaboration with Early Detection and Distribution Mapping Systems (EDDMapS; Wallace and Barger 2014).

In order to reach larger audiences and to expand manager-research communities, the RISCCs have worked to expand their respective listservs, which are a primary way that regions share resources, information, and build community. Across the five RISCC networks, over 2000 people are currently subscribed. Current TIE efforts are generally constrained by time and capacity within each RISCC group, and current efforts could increase through strategic recruitment of participants with specific skills (e.g., cooperative extension, science communication, Indigenous knowledge and perspectives). Additionally, due to developing virtual technologies and the Covid-19 Pandemic, many outreach and communication initiatives remain restricted to online events, which promotes inclusivity among a diversity of participants, reduces the carbon footprint for travel, and allows those from distant places to attend. However, in-person events can help participants build stronger and more meaningful relationships, which could help increase peer-peer knowledge exchange and lead to progress in creating climate-informed invasive species plans. Therefore, the RISCCs could benefit from additional monetary support that could facilitate more in-person workshops and events - particularly on high priority topics that are shared across regions such as managing range shifting taxa.

Implications for Future Management and Research

Our results highlight the ongoing need for both accessible information on high-priority research topics, such as resilience and range-shifters, and more information and products at finer spatial and temporal scales. As well, the results here demonstrate the need to include people from a

diversity of sectors and backgrounds in the development and implementation of research projects. In the U.S., coordinated federal invasive species management efforts at a national level are guided by NISC Management Plans (NISC, 2023). Established in 1999, and according to Executive Orders 13112 and 13751, the National Invasive Species Council (NISC) coordinates and supports federal efforts to address and prevent negative impacts of invasive species in the U.S. One of the core roles of NISC is to facilitate and support priority activities and efforts across multiple federal agencies and non-federal partners. Our work identifies several areas that could benefit from continued and increased monetary and personnel support from both federal organizations such as NISC and from boundary-spanning efforts such as those of RISCC.

Firstly, an often-cited limitation in our study to integrating climate change into invasive species management was the mismatch between the broad spatial and temporal scale for most climate change projections that are available and typically used in scientific literature, compared to the finer spatial and temporal scales at which management typically occurs. For example, global circulation models typically have a grid size that is hundreds of kilometers on a side, and many climate change projections are for mid and end-of-century (i.e., 2050 and 2100). Many management plans for parks and reserves, however, are typically for only 10-20 years, and managers tend to be most concerned with and work at the watershed scale. Addressing this barrier could include promoting research focused both on developing more locally relevant downscaled climate projections and investigating synergistic interactions between climate and invasive species on shorter timeframes (e.g., within 20-30 years) and at smaller spatial scales (e.g., the watershed and landscape scales). These products and findings would more closely match the scale at which management planning and operations are conducted (Archie et al., 2014; Beaury et al., 2020). This research focus could also simultaneously address an information gap that our results indicate limits the incorporation of climate change into invasive species management.

Secondly, invasive species management topics that are ranked as high priorities nationwide as well as regionally could present opportunities to foster and extend collaborative efforts at both the state and federal levels as well as between researchers and managers, leveraging the TIE framework to co-produce resources and management strategies. These shared high priority topics, such as identifying range shifting taxa, resilient ecosystems, and impacts of climate on control techniques, present an ideal opportunity for collaborative research, including translational ecology and knowledge co-production. This can help ensure that manager's research needs are met, that the science produced is usable, and that management considerations sections in peer-reviewed articles produced are practical and will lead to improved invasive species management. Additionally, current and future RISCC boundary-spanning efforts could be improved with additional interpersonal and informational support from federal agencies and personnel, such as those who work in the horizon scanning sector. These introductions and connections could be facilitated by NISC as an initial step towards increasing collaboration and sharing of resources or

information on high priority research and management topics, such as range shifting taxa and resilience ecosystems, identified in this survey.

Finally, finding and accessing the wealth of knowledge that has developed over the last two decades on the interactions between climate change and invasive species remains a challenge for both managers and researchers. Information is spread across multiple physical and digital repositories (Matzek et al., 2015), including species records, occurrence data, national and global databases, peer-reviewed literature, and technical reports, as well as web tools and applications. In addition to being scattered across academic and research institutes, information can also be stored and shared separately within either climate change or invasive species focused programs, despite the interacting effects of these two ecological stressors. Our work highlights the continual and growing need for reciprocal communication of this information not only between invasive species researchers and practitioners, but also with the public and between climate-and invasive species-focused programs, including those at the state and federal level. Increased communication and involvement, particularly with the public can have far-reaching benefits, including improving scientific and management literacy, and more cost-effective collection of data at relevant local or management scales (Danielsen et al., 2005).

To increase information exchange, educational and outreach tools, particularly those that focus on integrating invasive species into broader climate change efforts, could benefit from targeted support and development. Such work could include deliverables like the creation of searchable databases of invasive species management resources, including those generated by federal agencies, in a centralized and accessible location, media engagement. Deliverables could also include developing guidelines and examples of effective communication and outreach strategies, as well as educational resources that could be used by any interested invasive species researcher and practitioner to engage with their local community. An example of such educational and public outreach materials includes do-not-plant lists created by the NE RISCC, which detail invasive ornamental plants that the public should avoid planting in private or public gardens, as well as recommendations of natives to consider planting instead (Allen et al., 2022; Beaury, Patrick, et al., 2021; Bradley et al., 2020).

Survey Limitations and Opportunities

The survey efforts reported here represent an initial step in evaluating the priorities and challenges related to the management of both invasive species and climate change at a nationwide scale. Despite the broad geographic scope of this work, the five RISCC regions do not include all U.S. states and territories ([Appendix 3](#)). While some regions are likely underrepresented in the nationwide results, these results provide a foundation against which future surveys of RISCC TIE efforts can be assessed. Given the challenges associated with collecting survey data, we acknowledge that regional variation in survey results may be affected by differences in survey design and implementation across the RISCC regions. Each regional

RISCC survey was designed to address challenges and questions pertaining to invasive species management in their respective regions. This resulted in slight variation in the order and wording of questions and the response options presented to respondents. For example, the PI RISCC survey explicitly asked respondents to identify sources of useful *climate* information, whereas other RISCC surveys asked which information sources were most useful for informing management decisions in general, without the specific reference to climate. While survey design may affect the way that participants respond to survey questions, resources identified by PI respondents were similar to those from the other RISCC surveys. Survey differences did however present challenges in harmonizing results for nationwide analyses. For this reason, we opted to focus analyses at a nationwide scale on high priority topics shared across all RISCC surveys, while also highlighting regional-specific priorities separately. Moreover, many survey questions included answers or categories that were open to interpretation of respondents. For example, when answering questions related to perceived ‘organization/employer concern’, respondents may evaluate this perceived level of concern across any number of organization hierarchies (e.g., based on their own immediate local/regional working group, their regional office, or the organization as a whole (such as at a federal/national scale). Such response nuances are not currently captured in the analyses of survey questions.

We also recognize that differences in the geographic extent, time since establishment, and reach of communication of each Regional RISCC may contribute to variation in regional results. In terms of the survey data, the NE RISCC, established in 2016, covers a substantially larger terrestrial-based geographic area compared to the other RISCC regions (Figure 1, [Appendix 3](#)) and contributed 22% of the nationwide survey data. In contrast, respondents working in the NW RISCC region (established in 2020) covers a substantially smaller geographic region (Figure 1, [Appendix 3](#)) yet contributed one third of the data included in the nationwide results. Lastly, limitations on the respondent time and capacity of respondents to answer survey questions can alter data collected from surveys such as ours. These include survey fatigue, lack of incentive, and work-related stress - including stress due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The multiple surveys accounted for these as best as possible using multiple survey reminders, making surveys available across multiple weeks, and motivating survey responses via email solicitations and social media that emphasized how results will inform future RISCC activities and benefit RISCC members. Despite these limitations, these results provide the best information to date about the priorities and limitations of practitioners across the U.S. working at the intersection of invasive species and climate change.

Conclusion

Effectively addressing the dual and interacting threats of climate change and invasive species is an ongoing challenge and requires coordination in management strategies and regulations across multiple sectors. Yet, management of invasive species in a changing climate remains challenged

by common barriers, including lack of time, funding, personnel, and lack of information at locally relevant scales. Furthermore, despite the importance of early, proactive management, only 24% of invasive species work is dedicated towards emerging invasive species challenges — highlighting the urgent need for better science and policy centered around climate-informed invasive species management. Common high priority topics identified nationwide, including identifying and managing resilient ecosystems, range-shifting taxa, and understanding the impacts of climate change on control strategies indicate areas where additional funding and support could be most beneficial. Our work highlights the continual and growing need to support boundary-spanning efforts, such as those undertaken by the RISCC Management Networks, which help facilitate reciprocal communication and collaboration between invasive species researchers and practitioners. This work provides the best current overview of research and policy barriers and priorities associated with managing the interacting stressors of invasive species and climate change in the United States.

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not undergo IRB review, thus results presented here are for internal use and not for public publication.

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